

INFLUENCE OF CONTACTING, MATERIAL AND SHAPE ON THE RESISTANCE HEATING OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Especially in the automotive industry, continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics are currently experiencing a steadily increasing demand. Thermoplastic matrix systems promise shorter cycle times and improved joining and recycling characteristics when compared to fiber reinforced thermosets. In order to process continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics, semi-finished parts are usually produced first. These are afterwards heated and post-processed in a back injection molding process. This means that design elements such as load transfer elements and ribs are injected onto the usually flat semi-finished part. The effect of Joule heating can be exploited to heat the part. The electrically conductive carbon fibers are heated by an applied voltage. The temperature is then distributed through heat conduction into the part's thermoplastic matrix. By using Joule heating, high heating rates with low energy consumption are possible.

For the industrial use of Joule heating of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics, further correlations between influencing parameters must be investigated and specified. The part's shape in particular has a decisive influence on the quality of heating. Within the scope of this study, heating experiments are compared using a thermographic image system. In principle, rounded corners and small changes in shape result in homogeneous temperature distributions. Complex shapes should be avoided and design elements such as gaps, thickness steps and corners designed small compared to the overall area of the part.

1 INTRODUCTION

Automated and cost-efficient processing of continuous fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) can still be regarded as the main development goal for the series application of this extraordinary class of materials. In view of the objective of achieving the shortest possible process times, CFRPs with thermoplastic matrix systems are increasingly being used at present. Compared to already established thermoset matrix systems, thermoplastics open up new possibilities for shaping, joining, repair and recycling due to their ability to be remelted [1–4].

Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) are usually produced by forming semi-finished parts and subsequent back injection molding to increase part complexity. Significantly shorter cycle times can be achieved by saving the consolidation phase required to process thermosets. The cycle time is mainly determined by the heating and cooling process of the parts [1,4,5].

2 HEATING OF CRFTP

The common heating mechanisms contact heating and infrared radiation are already used industrially for heating CFRTP. Heating in infrared radiation furnaces, in particular, has become established for many applications and is optimised, for example by the use of several linear robot systems for pick-and-place operations during heating and complex control systems [6,7]. However, the variety of periphery requires an increased investment effort and the maximum heating speed is limited by a high system inertia and comparatively low efficiency. Thus an efficiency of 40 % [8] and maximum heating rates of 10 K/s [9] are achieved for parts with a thickness of 1 mm. The use of

contact heaters, on the other hand, has not been used widely despite the simple and cost-effective implementation, as the contact can cause damage to the part [7].

In both contact heating and heating by means of an infrared radiation furnace, heating takes place via an external energy source. As a result, the parts are heated from the outside; the energy penetrates only slightly into the inner core of the part, even with infrared radiation. Therefore, the heating of the core is mainly generated by heat conduction. This results in a temperature gradient along the part thickness, especially for thick-walled parts, so that temperatures at the surface are too high and the matrix is damaged while the core is not yet in a shapeable thermoelastic temperature range.

3 Joule Heating of CFRTP

James Prescott Joule discovered as early as 1850 that an electric current in a conductor is partially converted into thermal energy proportional the conductor's electrical resistance [10]. The material reduces the movement of the electrons induced by the electrical potential and thus decreases their kinetic energy. This energy is converted into heat. The principle of Joule heating is used in many applications. Immersion heaters and water boilers, but also seat and steering wheel heaters in automobiles are based on this principle. Joule heating is also already used in applications for CFRP, for example for resistance welding and accelerated consolidation of thermoset matrix systems [11–15].

In the context of this study, the principle of Joule heating is used to heat CFRTP during handling with an industrial robot system via direct contacting. Due to their excellent electrical conductivity, only carbon fibers are considered for this purpose.

In contrast to most other heating methods, a part can be heated from the inside over the entire volume by Joule heating [16]. On the one hand, this means that the part can be heated very uniformly and, on the other hand, that a high efficiency of theoretically more than 90 % [17] can be achieved, since only very low losses occur due to convection and heat conduction. The results of various basic investigations on resistance heating at the Institut für Kunststofftechnik of the University of Stuttgart have already been extensively published by Koslowski and others [17–20].

The requirements for a heating process for CFRTPs are mainly defined by three conflicting targets: Heating should be carried out as quickly, evenly and gently as possible. Accordingly, an optimum must be found, since various factors have an influence on the heating process. This study focuses on the influence of the part's shape on the resulting heating rate and temperature distribution. Additional experiments furthermore show the influence of the textile base material and the contacting.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND METHOD

Within the scope of this study, contact methods, part materials and part shapes for the Joule heating of CFRTP are compared and analyzed. First, suitable contacts are identified by determining the contact transfer resistance. Subsequently, heating tests are carried out and evaluated with a selection of shapes in the form of two full factorial Design of Experiments (DoE). Afterwards, two textile structures for carbon fibers are compared.

The contact transfer resistance depends on the material pairing, the contact pressure and the connecting contact surfaces. Copper is used as a contact material with varying surface pressures and contact surfaces, based on the results of previous investigations and due to its high electrical conductivity [17]. For measurement, a part is placed between two contacts in a universal testing machine from Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany and subjected to a compressive force. The measurement then takes place from contact piece to contact piece with the aid of a commercially available digital ohmmeter. Each measurement is repeated on five parts. A set of contact pieces is analyzed with different settings for size and contact force according to Table 1. The best results are used for the heating test stand.

The test stand (Figure 1) used for further investigations is based on thermal image processing to monitor heating rate and temperature distribution of the parts during heating. An external power supply PS9000 3U by EA Elektro-Automatik GmbH, Viersen, Germany, provides power at up to 340 A while allowing voltages up to 80 V (DC). The thermal imaging system VarioCAM HDx 615S by InfraTec, Dresden, Germany, calibrated from -40 °C to 600 °C with a resolution of 0.03 K is used for temperature data acquisition. A universal testing machine is used to apply the contact force.

Factor	Unit	Setting 1	Setting 2	Setting 3
contact width	mm	3	6	12
contact length	mm	25	25	25
contact force	kN	5	10	15

Table 1: Parameters for contact resistance measurement.

Figure 1. Schematic of the test stand used for the evaluation of Joule heating of CFRTP.

Current, voltage and other processing parameters are recorded during each experiment using LabVIEW® by National Instruments, Austin, Texas, USA, and post-processed using the open source python programming language. The test specimen are organosheets by Bond Laminates GmbH, Brilon, Germany, of type TEPEX® dynalite 201C200/45% with a PA66 matrix system and a carbon fiber volume fraction of 45 % unless otherwise specified.

The shapes of the test specimen are varied in two ways. A first test series focuses on gaps in rectangular parts. The parts are cut according to ISO 527-4 type 2 to 25 mm width and 150 mm length at a thickness of 1 mm. Gaps in form of circular cutouts with 5 and 10 mm width (hole diameter) are then drilled into the part, once in the middle of the part, and once off-centered, according to Figure 2. The settings result in a 2² full factorial design as shown in Table 2.

The second test series focuses on design elements in form of steps in part width (Figure 2, right). The part shapes are cut to “L”-form in such a way that different steps in width occur along the long side of the part. The length and thickness of the parts are equal to the first test series and the overall volume of each part is constant. Corners are rounded in order to determine if this improves the overall heating quality.

Factor	Unit	Setting “-“	Setting “+”
gap position	-	centered	off-centered
gap diameter	mm	5	10
step width	mm	5	10
corner roundness	mm	0	2

Table 2: Factors for the analysis of the contact shape influence.

Shape	Features	Shape	Features
	gap centered gap diameter = 5 mm		step step width: 22.5 mm to 27.5 mm roundness = 0 mm
	gap centered gap diameter = 5 mm		step step width: 22.5 mm to 27.5 mm roundness = 2 mm
	gap centered gap diameter = 10 mm		step step width: 25 mm to 30 mm roundness = 0 mm
	gap centered gap diameter = 10 mm		step step width: 25 mm to 30 mm roundness = 2 mm

Figure 2. Parts with gaps and parts with steps in width direction as viewed from above.

Each parameter setup is repeated two times with virgin test specimens, each specimen is tested two times. The direction of the current is swapped between tests to account for possible effects. All tests are carried out with a current related to the cross section of the part of 0.64 A/mm^2 relative to a rectangular bar of 25 mm width and 1 mm thickness. The voltage adjusts according to the overall resistance of the part and contacting.

After ten seconds heating time, the complete temperature field of the thermal imaging system is saved and evaluated. The temperatures at two characteristic lines in the parts are measured, once through the design element and once in an area, where the influence of the design element is considered minimal. The positioning of the characteristic lines is carried out according to Figure 3 and Figure 4.

For further evaluation, the maximum part temperature and the relative temperature difference are measured as responses of the DoE. The relative temperature difference is calculated as the ratio of maximum part temperature to average part temperature as measured in an area where the design element does not affect the temperature distribution (see the light blue lines in Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. Characteristic lines in a part with an off-centered gap.

Figure 4. Characteristic lines in a part with a step in width.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Effects of contacting on the Joule heating of CFRTP

Several different contact pieces are analyzed in respect to their quality of electrical contact to the CFRTP. Figure 5 shows the influence of different contacting methods on the contact transfer resistance as box plots. The line surrounded by the box is the mean value and the box is confined by the upper and lower quadruple, consisting of 50 % of the total data. Whiskers show the standard deviation.

Figure 5. Contact resistance through a part with different contact piece sizes and contact forces

Copper contacts with different widths and contact forces are analyzed. For contact pieces wider than 6 mm, improved contact quality can be determined if the contact force is constant. This corresponds to findings in previous research [17,19]. Additionally, higher contact forces result in a lower contact resistance and considerably less scattering of the measurements. Therefore, high contact forces and wide contacts are expected to yield the best results during Joule heating. Especially, repeatability of the heating process could be improved significantly.

For an industrial implementation of Joule heating, e. g. in a robotic handling system, these findings have a particular meaning: High contact forces result in a bigger clamping system and higher inertia of the overall system, which requires larger and more expensive robot systems, increasing the necessary investment.

4.2 Effects of gaps on the Joule heating of CFRTP

The DoE for the analysis of the influence of the part's shape is evaluated with regard to two target responses: The maximum part temperature and the relative temperature difference. The maximum part temperature allows the analysis of critical part temperatures which could damage fiber and matrix while at the same time, the difference between maximum part temperature and average temperature should not be too high to guarantee formability and good adhesion between semi-finished part and plastic melt during back injection molding.

Figure 6 shows the maximum part temperature depending on different factor settings for parts with gaps. A high value of an effect indicates a high influence of this factor on the respective response. Additionally, the significance level determined by ANOVA [21] is specified for each effect; smaller values indicate high statistical relevance.

Figure 6. Effects and interactions of the factors gap width and gap position to maximum part temperature.

As can be determined by comparison of the two factors, the gap width has a high effect on the maximum part temperature, while the position of the gap has no effect. The effect of the gap width can be lead back to the density of electrical current. For the total width of the part of 25 mm, a current of 16 A is applied. The gap results in a reduction of the part width and thus an increase in electrical current density from 0.64 A/mm^2 to above 1 A/mm^2 for gap widths of 10 mm. Hence, higher energy input occurs and the part locally heats up faster. In the case of 10 mm gap width, this can lead to particularly high temperatures even above the decomposition temperature of the respective matrix systems. As can be determined from the right graph shown in Figure 6, almost no interaction between the factors can be determined.

The relative temperature difference is shown in Figure 7. The results correspond to the results shown for the maximum part temperature. This means, that in both cases the overall part temperature is distributed relatively homogenously while especially the area near the design element experiences greater temperature differences. For gap widths of 10 mm, the difference between average and maximum temperature is about 70 % which complicates processing: in order to reach processing temperatures in all areas of the part, areas with design elements get damaged by high temperatures. If, for example, an average processing temperature of $280 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is reached, temperatures of over $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ might occur in areas with design elements. This effect can be minimized by using smaller design elements. Gap widths of 5 mm result in only 20 % higher maximum temperatures compared to the average part temperature.

Figure 7. Effects and interactions of the factors gap width and gap position to relative temperature difference.

4.3 Effects of steps in thickness on the Joule heating of CFRTP

Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the effects of the analyzed factors for parts in “L”-form. As with parts with gaps, the size of the design element (in this case the step size) has a significant effect on the maximum part temperature and the relative temperature difference. Rounded corners, in contrast, have a low effect which is not statistically significant. However, the corner radius appears to have an influence for small step sizes as can be determined by the interaction effect (Figure 9, right). In this case, rounded corners appear to improve the overall heating quality. As can be seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4, the change in temperature due to changes in part width occurs much less pronounced as with the gaps and the overall temperature distribution is much more homogeneous.

Figure 8. Effects and interactions of the factors step width and corner roundness to maximum part temperature.

Figure 9. Effects and interactions of the factors step width and corner roundness to relative temperature difference.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The Joule heating of CFRTP represents a promising approach for processing of this extraordinary group of materials and promises fast and efficient processing into complex structural parts with functional integration.

In this study, the influence of contact width and contact force on the contact transfer resistance as well as the influence of shape changes on the heating process are analysed. In general, larger contact areas and higher contact forces lead to lower contact transfer resistances, ensuring better electrical conduction from the contacting into the part and thus improving the heating process.

Design elements such as gaps and steps in width should be designed as small as possible to avoid temperature damage and inhomogeneous heating. Rounded corners may further improve the temperature distribution if the size of the gaps and widths is small enough.

In future investigations, complex shapes will be contacted with two or more separate electrical circuits in order to investigate if the temperature distribution can thus be improved. The Joule heating approach is then integrated into a robot handling system in order to automatically heat semi-finished parts during transportation to an injection moulding machine.

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